

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2021"

IN ENGLISH STORIES "MYSTERIOUS KILLING OF A DOG AT NIGHT"

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Annotation: *This article focuses on the topic of parenting in modern adolescent literature. The authors consider the problem of the relationship between parents and children in the example of Mark Haddon's "Mysterious killing of a dog at night" and prove that adults have a high level of responsibility in families with separate children, because he includes many psychological and social problems that go beyond family relationships. Addressing M. Haddon not only gives a new perspective on the lives of children with special needs, but also allows them to understand what challenges their parents have to overcome, and how ready they are to change and accept the situation.*

Keywords: *perspective, adolescent, distinctive, protagonist's, teenager.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola zamonaviy o'smirlar adabiyotidagi ota-onalar mavzusiga qaratilgan. Mualliflar ota-onalar va bolalar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar muammosini Mark Xeddonning "Tunda itni sirli o'ldirish" asari misolida ko'rib chiqadilar va alohida farzandli oilalarda kattalarning mas'uliyati yuqori ekanligini isbotlaydilar, chunki u ko'plab psixologik va ijtimoiy muammolarni o'z ichiga oladi. oilaviy munosabatlardan tashqariga chiqadigan muammolar. M.Xaddonga murojaat qilish nafaqat alohida ehtiyojli bolalar hayotiga yangi nuqtai nazarni beradi, balki ularga ota-onalari qanday qiyinchiliklarni engish kerakligini, vaziyatni o'zgartirishga va qabul qilishga qanchalik tayyorligini tushunishga imkon beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *istiqbolli, o'smirlilik, o'ziga xos, bosh qahramon, o'smir.*

INTRODUCTION. In modern adolescent literature, questions arise that are important for the formation of personality, e.g. as the search and acceptance of oneself and the world around oneself, the determination of moral values, the formation of life principles and relationships. However, in our opinion, the issues addressed by the authors of the works of art are the role of parents in children's lives.

The phenomenon of parenthood is studied by psychologists and sociologists. Thus, "parenting is now seen as a process of promoting the child's progressive development and

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achieving autonomy in a benevolent, safe, and psychologically comfortable environment created by parental behavior”¹. Addressing this topic is especially relevant in our time, as I. A. Komarova noted and O. V. Poida, “this is accompanied by many unfavorable factors of economic, social, environmental, and other nature that have not occurred before, the connection with which requires more parental authority”.

It should be noted that the theme of “fathers and children” is not new to literature, but in works about adolescents it takes on a new meaning as it raises questions about the fundamentals and attitudes of different generations as distinctive features. . the relationship between parents and their adolescent children. Many psychologists point out that adolescence is associated with a rethinking of the value system, manifestations of youth maximalism, protest against adult supervision and proof its independence. Children this age present themselves as independent individuals make a decision. However, attempts at rapid growth often lead to unintended consequences, therefore, parental involvement should not be limited to solving and transferring material problems ethical conversations require patience, understanding, psychological support and assistance in any situation life situation.

Modern authors describe different models of family relationships and try to convey to the reader the idea that parents play a key role in the development of a child’s personality. In this context The issue of separate consideration requires the topic of parents of children with special needs. The article analyzes the British work "The Mysterious Night Killing of a Dog" author Mark Haddon won the Whitbred Prize and the Boeke Prize for his novel.

¹ Zhelyabina A., Igonina S., Pavlova T. Traditions and innovations in contemporary British educational novel // Language and Education. 2017. Vol. 31. Iss. 6. P. 828-834

Fifteen-year-old Christopher Bun, who suffers from Asperger syndrome, has excellent memory and excellent math skills. For Haddon's reliability fills his work with diagrams, graphs, maps, tables that allow him to assess the abilities of the protagonist and look at the world around him with his eyes. According to the behavioral characteristics, the teenager attends a special school. So Christopher doesn't like it when even very close people touch him, and if that happens, he immediately starts screaming and can even hit. He doesn't need to communicate, he can't talk to anyone for long. He is very fast in food: the products on the plate should be of a certain color and not touch each other and in general, he does not eat or drink anything for a long time. The hero, “investigating the murder of a neighbor's dog, reveals another, much more significant, secret. Christopher learns that his mother, it turns out, did not die, as everyone around him told him, but ran away, unable to withstand the peculiarities of her son's behavior, which is more befitting of a young child". The boy is brought up by his father, who solves all his everyday problems, acts as an intermediary between Christopher and the outside world, and resolves conflict situations. He, knowing the features his son, accepts them and does not violate the designated boundaries. So, father never hugs Christopher, because it causes irritation and aggression. The most that the son allows is the contact of the fingertips: “We do this because sometimes the father wants to hug me, but I don't love, when they touch me, so

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we touch each other a little, and this means that my father loves me". The author quite realistically described the situation where one of the parents, unable to bear the difficulties associated with raising a special child, leaving the family. "I wasn't a very good mother, Christopher. Maybe if events had developed differently, if you had been different, everything would have been different. But, unfortunately, everything turned out the way it did."

Fearing for his life, the teenager runs away from home and searches for his mother in London. He says he will live with her, because he is afraid that his father, having killed the dog, might kill him too. Ed makes attempts to win back his son, but he is adamant, as he cannot get rid of the obsessive feeling that he is lying to him.

Mark Haddon, using the example of his novel, convincingly proves that raising special children requires a lot of strength and patience. It is not possible for everyone to overcome such trials alone, since constant psychological support is required. The protagonist's parents don't find her friend in a friend, which leads not just to a break in relations, but to the search for a person on the side who could compensate for the lack of understanding and care in the family. For Jude, Christopher's mother, that person is their neighbor Mr. Shears, who moments gave her support and attention. He was the only person, by her own admission, to whom she could pour out her soul, tell about her experiences, without fear of looking helpless and weak. Roger helped her cope with a difficult life situation, from him she received that care and affection, which she was deprived in her own family. Common experiences associated with betrayal and betrayal of spouses bring Ed together for some time and Mrs Shears. It is in her that Christopher's father tries to find support. Eileen often visited their house, helping with cleaning, cooking. Mr. Boone regarded her care and attention as an opportunity to start a new relationship and find joint happiness. In her face, he wanted to see a mother for his son. However, Mrs Shears not ready to take responsibility and care for a partner, and even more so for his child. Over time, he realized that neither he nor even Christopher needed Eileen. She does not want to change her usual way of life and sacrifice her comfort for the sake of a relationship that was burdensome for her: "... it is much easier for her to live alone, looking after a single mongrel, than to link her fate with living people".

As a result, none of Christopher's parents manage to arrange their personal lives, because their new partners do not want to participate in the upbringing of someone else's child with inadequate and unpredictable behavior. The heroes, thinking about the question: "Is it possible to be happy knowing that your child, incapable of independence, is betrayed and abandoned by you?", Come to a compromise that allows both of them to take care of their son. The author reserves the right for the characters to realize and correct mistakes. The path that parents take teenager, allows them to understand what role the son plays in their life, and realize the full degree of responsibility.

CONCLUSION. The peculiarity of Christopher makes them "grow up", grow up and change: they begin to solve problems, rather than run away from them, learn to sacrifice themselves, to realize that a child is part of their world, and not a burden. Thus, Mark

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Haddon touches on the topical issue for modern society, not only about children with developmental disabilities, but also about the infantilism of their parents. Many families break up because adults are not ready for the difficulties of family life. The very fact of the appearance of a child does not make the relationship stronger, on the contrary, it adds problems that seem insoluble if the child has any "deviations". Using the example of a private situation, the author shows that in order to build strong family relationships, everyone requires dedication, responsibility, support in any life situation, desire solve problems together, find compromises.

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